

Deliverable D2.1

ETES and components requirements and KPIs for each use case

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Cuerva*

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TURBODEN

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
COP	Coefficient Of Performance
ETES	Electro-Thermal Energy Storage
GPP	Geothermal Power Plant
HTHP	High Temperature Heat Pump
HP	High Pressure
IP	Intermediate Pressure
IWH	Industrial Waste Heat
KZD	Kizildere
LP	Low Pressure
NG	Natural Gas
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PFD	Process Flow Diagram
RTE	Round Trip Efficiency
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

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1. About the project

SEHRENE's new electrothermal energy storage (ETES) concept is designed to store renewable electricity (RE) and heat and to reconstitute it as needed. It is very energy-efficient (80-85%), is geographically independent and uses no critical raw materials. It enables 8-12 times longer storage duration than Li-ion, with LCOS of 80 – 137 €/MWh, depending on the use-case. This is lower than pumped hydro, the lowest-cost commercial electricity storage. Its lifetime of 20-30 years is 2 – 3x longer than Li-ion. A TRL4 prototype and the digital twins of 3 full use-cases will be delivered: (i) ceramics plant storing excess, on-site PV power in a micro-grid and industrial waste-heat for continuous green H₂ production and self-consumption, (ii) a smart-grid, and (iii) a geothermal power plant. The ETES integrates: (i) a novel heat-pump design with a coefficient of performance of 50% the theoretical maximum, (ii) a novel thermal energy storage system with energy density of 90 kWh/m³ (+30%), containing phase-change material in a novel metallic Kelvin cells-like foam and (iii) ORC with novel operating parameters. New digital tools will optimise the energy management of the storage and facilitate investment decisions by potential end-users taking LCA and technical-economic factors into account. SEHRENE unites 5 R&D teams with top-level expertise in prototyping, physics-based modelling, characterisation and digital twins of thermo-electric systems, thermal storage and AI-based energy-management; 1 industrial Heat Pump and ORC manufacturer, 1 RE producer, 1 DSO, 1 ceramics company, 1 SME developing decision-support tools, and 1 SME for dissemination and communication. The exploitation plan aims to implement the solution in the first factory in 2029. SEHRENE's market penetration will enable to capture 1% of the market by 2040 avoiding 90Mm³ of NG and 15Mt CO₂/year. R&D and industrial partners project to generate 5.8M€ in revenues by 2035 from sales of heat pumps, thermal storage, ORC, licenses to R&D results and consulting services.

In summary, SEHRENE introduces an innovative Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) solution, addressing a critical technological challenge faced by conventional ETES systems - round-trip efficiencies diminished by temperature losses. This disruptive architecture not only resolves this issue but also positions itself as a viable option to meet Europe's energy transition requirements.

Consortium

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2. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the three use cases selected for initial analysis regarding integration of ETES which will be developed in SEHRENE Project. Three industry use cases will be;

- Zorlu Enerji KZD-II Geothermal Power Plant
- TORRECID Ceramic Frit Facility
- CUERVA Electricity Distribution Grid

In this deliverable, first the three use cases will be defined briefly to provide background information on the industries. The normal operation will be explained and possible ETES integration options will be explained. For integration, crucial parameters differing from industries will be taken into consideration, such as temperature, pressure, flow or currents.

This deliverable aims to provide general overview of the industries as well as the optimizations that will be added with the integration of the electro-thermal energy storage systems. SEHRENE Project will use this deliverable as a source for other work packages, focusing in LCA, optimizations and designing of the ETES.

3. Introduction

In an era defined by pressing energy challenges and escalating carbon emissions, the imperative for sustainable solutions has reached critical proportions. The existing energy landscape has several inefficiencies, where traditional methods of energy generation often fall short in meeting the escalating demands of modern society. Additionally, the increase in carbon emissions adds to environmental degradation, precipitating dire consequences for global ecosystems and human well-being. While the urgency of mitigating climate change increases, innovative approaches to energy storage emerge as pivotal avenues for combating both energy scarcity and carbon footprint.

Electro Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) is one of the sustainable energy solutions which requires more investigation. By harnessing the unused energy in industries and providing storage, ETES offers a multifaceted approach to address the intertwined challenges of energy storage and carbon emissions. Through its heat pump backed storage mechanisms, ETES not only enhances the reliability and efficiency of energy delivery but it will also facilitate the seamless integration of renewable energy sources into the grid. Moreover, by providing a means to store excess renewable energy during periods of low demand, ETES effectively mitigates the intermittency issues plaguing renewable energy adoption, thereby fostering a more resilient and sustainable energy infrastructure.

As the world stands at a pivotal juncture in its transition towards a low-carbon future, the imperative to expedite the deployment of innovative energy storage solutions like ETES has never been more urgent. By encouraging energy resilience, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, and curbing carbon emissions, ETES epitomizes the transformative potential of sustainable technology in directing in a cleaner, more sustainable energy sector. As such, this project aims to delve into the intricacies of ETES, exploring its feasibility, scalability, and potential impact in addressing the dual challenges of energy security and environmental sustainability.

In this deliverable, we will delve into three distinct use case industries to assess the applicability and effect of Electro Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) in diverse operational contexts. By studying the unique energy demands, operational constraints of each industry, we aim to illuminate the specific advantages and challenges of integrating ETES within their respective infrastructures. Through a comprehensive analysis of these use cases, we aim to provide actionable insights and recommendations design for the requirements of each sector, and create pathways for other sectors, thereby facilitating the widespread adoption of ETES as a transformative solution for enhancing energy efficiency and reducing carbon emissions across various industrial domains.

4. Use cases definition for ETES requirement

4.1 Use Case 1: Zorlu Enerji Kızıldere-II GPP

4.1.1 Kızıldere Site Description

Kızıldere geothermal field, as shown in the Figure 1 and Figure 2, is situated at the western branch of Büyük Menderes Graben within the limits of Denizli Province. It is Turkey's first and high-potential geothermal field explored for energy generation purposes.

The first geological and geophysical surveys in the Kızıldere geothermal field began in 1965, and were carried out by the state-owned Turkish Mineral Research and Exploration Co. (MTA). The first geothermal reservoir was discovered in 1968 with a geothermal well drilled in 540 m depth, which had a source temperature of 198°C. In the years from 1968 to 1973, a total of 16 geothermal wells were drilled to depths ranging between 370–1,241 m. Six of the 17 geothermal wells were found feasible for electricity generation.

Figure 1 Kızıldere Field in Geothermal Potential Map by MTA

Lithologically, the Kızıldere geothermal reservoir is surrounded by marble and limestone rocks containing plentiful carbon dioxide. The calcium carbonate dissolves from the rocks and later gets deposited as limescale on the instruments in the geothermal well and at the brink, such as demisters, heat exchangers, and other locations, and this causes a drop in pressure. This results in decreased steam production, reduced efficiency, and an increased probability of failure. Thus, the power plant capacity was reduced to

6 MW before privatization in 2008. To prevent calcium carbonate scaling in production wells, inhibitors are used.

The geothermal fluid of Kızıldere reservoir has a Langelier Saturation Index (LSI) of 2.1 and Ryznar Stability Index (RSI) of 2.3 by a pH value of 9.3, making scaling take place very rapidly.

The source temperature at the first reservoir is between 240–260°C. All the geothermal fluid used in the power plant is reinjected into the reservoir for the purpose of maintaining the sustainability of the source.

In addition to electricity generation, the geothermal fluid serves for processing of carbon dioxide gas as a byproduct, and this is used in dry ice production at two nearby plants. The total annual dry ice production in Kızıldere is 80,000 tons. Further applications are heating of 500 decares greenhouse space and 2,500 households.

Figure 2 Geographical Map of Kızıldere Geothermal Field

4.1.2 Kızıldere-II Geothermal Power Plant

Kızıldere 2 GPP, having 80 MWe installed capacity, runs with triple flash and binary combined cycle technology which allows to reach higher power outputs through advanced steam turbine technology. Kızıldere 2 GPP has 12 production wells which enters the process via High Pressure (HP) Separator and also Kızıldere 1's brine is sent to Low Pressure (LP) Separator to enhance the productivity. Kızıldere 1 and Kızıldere 2 power plants share a common re-injection infrastructure via set of brine injection pumps which increases the brine's pressure up to 35 bar(a) to ensure the sustainability of the reservoir.

Kızıldere 2 GPP was designed as a combined heat and power (CHP) production facility. 80 MWe installed electricity capacity corresponds to the consumption of 400,000 households, 20 MWt installed district heating capacity corresponds to the demand of 2,500 households and 30 MWt installed greenhouse heating capacity is able to supply heat to 500 hectares of vegetable greenhouses. (Halaçoğlu et al., 2018)

Figure 3 General layout of the Kizildere-II geothermal power plant

The production wells transfer 2,678.5 tph of geothermal fluid at average of 10.65 bar(a) and 165°C to HP separator. Then the brine in HP separator is separated into saturated steam and saturated water conditions at 8.45 bar(a). Steam quality of the brine is around 13.8% in this pressure value according to the design conditions resulting approximately 370 tph of steam to enter the HP turbine. Remaining portion of the geothermal fluid continues the process and throttled into the Intermediate Pressure (IP) Separator at 4.15 bar(a) and 144°C. IP Separator operates at 4.15 bar(a) and separates nearly the 5.5% of the steam from the brine to enter the IP turbine. Remaining portion is called IP brine and it is throttled and combined with 1,000 tph of Kızıldere 1's HP brine before being separated in LP separator at 1.2 bar(a) and 110°C. Steam quality in these conditions are calculated to be 6.6% and around 210 tph of steam enters the LP turbine. HP, IP and LP turbines are all mounted to the same shaft and transmit the torque to a common generator for 60 MW electricity generation at the end. 20 MWe is generated in bottoming cycle which gains heat and energy from HP turbine exhaust as shown in Figure 1. Kızıldere 2 GPP also have 2 heat exchangers units which one of them is designed to be used for district heating purposes with 20 MWt and the other one is

4.1.3 ETES Integration to KZD-II GPP

This section describes the possible configuration of the ETES integration in the KZD-II GPP. The energy sources corresponding to Industrial Waste Heat (IHW) are identified and classified according to the energy potential, i.e. the capacity to supply energy at high temperatures. The ETES integration aims to use part of the IHW to thermally upgrade the quality using a High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP). The heat is then stored in the Phase Change Material (PCM) storage so that, when the KZD-II GPP operators decide to discharge the PCM they can generate electricity through an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC). This could allow for different operating contributions of the ETES in the case study, such as:

- This increases the flexibility of the actual KZD-II plant giving the advantage of storing electricity when the Turkish electricity grid prices are lower, and selling electricity when the prices are higher (energy arbitrage).
- Peak shaving and congestion services, and energy storage in case of blackouts.
- The system provides the possibility to cover part of the energy demand of the auxiliary components of the plants (pumps, fans, etc.) increasing the gross power of the plant.

According to the PFD of the KZD-II provided by Zorlu, a three-flash plant with a binary cycle can be identified. The potential points as energy sources which could be integrated into the ETES are presented in Table 2. The higher temperature corresponds to the extraction well fluid, which corresponds to point 1 in the P&ID. A second energetic vector identified is the brine reinjection wells in point 8 of the P&ID and point 58 which corresponds to the circulating water loop. The selection of this point on the ETES could generate different configurations and performance. However, as a starting point, the n°8 is highlighted as the higher temperature available and will be considered as the study source. Point n°1 is discarded as a coupled energy point, as it could strongly affect the operation of the KZD-II because this fluid goes directly to the first flash plant. For the cold side of the ORC, point 64 could be used as it does not affect the operation of the system and also presents a large cold source to be integrated into the ETES. Increasing the ORC performance in this case can be achieved using ambient air (as long as it is at a lower temperature than point 64).

Table 2 Properties of the points of interest of the PFD of the GPP KZD-II.

PFD point	T [°C]	P [bar]	M_dot [ton/h]	Fluid
1	178.1	10.65	2678.5	97% steam/brine
8	113.1	1.59	3088.6	100% steam/brine
58	50.6	3	283.9	99.9% condensate water
64	24.1	3.63	9000	100% cooling water

The GPP KZD-II plant is a base load generator, so we can consider that the waste heat production is almost the whole day and at their nominal conditions. The possibilities that could be considered:

- Direct coupling of point 8 with the ORC to produce electricity. This option increases the efficiency of the plant, as part of the heat is recovered. Couple point 8 with a HTHP to increase the temperature stored in the PCM and then discharged by the ORC. This will increase system flexibility and energy production.
 - Here, several options for integration of the IWH within the ORC operation could be analysed:
 - IWH as a superheater
 - IWH as a preheater
 - IWH as an evaporator

The project will consider the second possibility as it can increase the flexibility of the plant, making energy arbitrage and also because increases the gross power of the ORC. The first case will be compared for KPI#T27, to establish the main advantages of the ETES integration.

The case study advantages can be listed as:

- Permanent and constant conditions of the reinjection well water (base load plant).
- Energy arbitrage, consumption of electricity when it is cheap and sale when it is expensive.
- Flexibility of the system to cover the electricity demand of auxiliary components.
- Peak savings through the ETES and ancillary services.

The ETES will increase the gross power of the KZD-II plant, given the availability to dedicate and produce this excess power during the periods of interest for KZD-II. Figure 5 presents the main idea of the integration of the ETES. Note that this is only an illustration of the ideas of the SEHRENE project.

Figure 5 Example of the ETES Integration in the KZD-II GPP.

The integration of the ETES could operate during the whole day and the availability of the IWH could be considered fixed, as KZD-II is a renewable power plant that operates as a base load on the electricity grid. According to the operation load, the brine mass flow rate at point n°8 (3088.5 tonnes/h) could decrease or increase. However, the ETES operation aims to operate in the following conditions:

- The ETES will be charged by 4 hours by the HTHP
 - Within a condenser thermal power of $4h \cdot 7\text{MW}_{\text{th}} = 28 \text{MW}_{\text{th}}$.
 - If the COP reach 5 the electricity inputs correspond to $5.6 \text{MW}_e\text{h}$.
- The ETES will be discharged in 2 hours by the ORC
 - The gross power produced corresponds to 2MW_e , reaching a total value of $4\text{MW}_e\text{h}$, leading an ORC efficiency of 14.3%.

The technical principles of the case study correspond to:

- The electricity demand of the auxiliary components corresponds to 10.688MW_e for the flash plant and 3.7MW_e for the binary plant, giving a total value of 14.388MW_e .
- The minimum temperature that the waste heat can reach is 85°C , avoiding the generation of scaling.
- There is no renewable electricity generation in the study area that could be used to power the ETES.

For the ETES integration:

- The operation PCM temperature must be assessed aiming to reach the desired operational conditions ($\text{RTE} > 80\%$, $\text{COP} \geq 50\%$ of theoretical COP).
- The integration of the IWH in the ORC must be evaluated, analysing which is the best trade-off (as an evaporator, pre-heater, or superheater aiming to improve the performance).

One of the possible configurations of integrating the energy sources in the ETES is presented in Figure 6. Here, the brine mix is taken in point 8, to be used in the HTHP, where the energy given by the compressor is directly transferred to the PCM storage. Later, the ORC uses the PCM as the evaporator to convert the refrigerant into vapour to produce electricity in the expander. In order to increase the output power, point 8, is employed as a pre-heater in the ORC mode. This figure does not take into account the technical specifications as well as the valves that must be incorporated for the operation of the system.

Figure 6 Possible ETES integration in the KZD-II GPP.

This configuration is evaluated under the conditions depicted above corresponding to; a HTHP of 7 MW_{th}, and a charge and discharge time of 4 and 2 hours, respectively. The PCM temperature considered corresponds to 150°C, this is an arbitrary value which will be the result of the following work package. Under these conditions, the ETES produce an electricity power in the expander of 2.62 MWe, with an ORC efficiency of 15.7%. On the other hand, the HTHP power consumption corresponds to 1.28 MWe, with a COP of 5.5. The ratio of Energy discharge (in electricity) on Energy charge (in electricity) is beyond 100% in this configuration thanks to the increase of energy production at the ORC turbine with the additional IWH at the pre-heater, whereas without such integration of the IWH in the ORC, this ratio is lower but quite high at 83%. This proposed configuration has the advantages of a high electricity storage capacity and the availability to increase the gross power of the system.

Through the technical limitations and operational constraints, it is possible to describe some steps for future ETES design work:

- The ORC and HTHP could operate off-design for partial or low-load operation of the KZD-II, the annual frequency and power of these conditions must be taken into account for the system design.
- The heat transfer between the PCM and the hot heat exchangers could be affected for PCM qualities close to 0% and 100%.
- The space available for PCM storage and the requirements of the PCM (sensitivity to certain ambient temperatures, radiation, earthquakes, etc.).

- Strategic operation for the peak-shaving and electricity arbitrage.
- The system is not affected by weather conditions, as it depends on the Turkish electricity operators, who decide either to keep it on or off.
- Design the first reference ETES, based on current work and experimental experience.
- Numerical modelling for the components that integrate the ETES.
- Economic indicators and comparison within the different possible ETES integration.
- System and components optimization for the optimal solution.

4.2 Use Case 2: TORRECID Ceramic Frit Facility

4.2.1 Site Description and melting frit description

TORRECID S.A. is located in town of Alcora, in the province of Castellón (Spain), as it is indicated in Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 7. Geographical situation of TORRECID S.A.

Figure 8. Geographical situation of TORRECID S.A.

Figure 9. TORRECID S.A. facilities in Alcora (Spain)

4.2.1.1 Frit smelting process

There is some variability inherent to the production of frits. Although certain raw materials may lead to obtain an equivalent desired chemical composition, changes in their mineralogical composition may lead to changes in the melting conditions, generated fumes and associated productivity.

TORRECID has 30 frit smelters in their facilities in Spain. Frit smelter has a main burner based of natural gas combined with air or oxygen. During the melting process, different raw materials are fused to generate a melted mixture. Each raw material has its own storage silo. Following the recipe, each raw material is transported to a weighing station.

There are two weighing stations: one for materials that are used in greater amounts and another one for materials that are added in smaller quantities. After weighing, raw materials are transported to mixers. The mix is transported to a storage silo behind each frit smelter. From the silo, materials are carried to a hopper that feeds them to the screw conveyor that leads them to the smelter.

The hopper has two level sensors to indicate when it is empty or full in order to activate and deactivate the feeding, respectively.

Figure 10. Storage silo & hopper.

Figure 11. Screw conveyor.

This mixture is incorporated into the raft of the kiln and advances inside the smelter. During this process, productivity is assessed through visualizing the height of the heap (which is referred to as “Montón”) through a looking glass, which should be at a certain predetermined level.

Figure 12. View through the looking glass inside the smelter.

Operators determine such height by inspecting it visually. Once the mixture is completely melted, this mixture flows out by overflow by a special piece that is at the exit, which we call tongue. Then the smelted mix is subsequently poured in a water bath, cooling it sharply. This process is called quenching. Quenching process transforms the melted frit into a fragmented solid material insoluble in water. From the water bath, frit is transported by a belt to the receiving cup.

Figure 13. View of exit of melted frit.

Figure 14. Ceramic frit solidified after quenching process.

Each cup has two contact sensors and have an opening that releases the frit on the bag receiver called big bag. This orifice is opened a number of times during each batch taking into account the produced frit.

Figure 15. Big bag feeding process.

4.2.1.2 Fumes emissions

Fumes exit from the smelter through a lateral opening. Those fumes are diluted with air with a fan prior to their inlet to a heat exchanger located before the bag filters. In the heat exchanger, fumes are cooled down with ambient air which leaves the system at 600 K (326 °C). Those cooled fumes are filtered through the bag filters in order to avoid the emissions of particles and the emitted outside.

The following table summarized the main process parameters in the frit production.

Table 3. Process parameters in the frit production process.

Energy & Mass flows					
Id.	Description	Type	Amount	Units	T °C
RM	Raw materials	MASS	1000	kg/h	25
F	FRIT	MASS	1000	Kg/h	1550
NG	Natural gas for frits melting (0%H ₂ SUBSTITUTION)	MASS	130	Nm ³ /h	25
O ₂	Oxygen for combustion (0%H ₂ SUBSTITUTION)	MASS	270	Nm ³ /h	25
WELTZ	Water needed for electrolyse process	MASS	4,5	kg/h	25
EXF	Exhaust fumes exiting the smelter	MASS	5000	Nm ³ /h	300

4.2.2 ETES Integration to TORRECID Facility

As it is described in the project proposal, TOR use case is a smelter producing frits at 1550 °C using natural gas (NG) today and aiming to substitute some NG with hydrogen later. ETES will be able to use industrial exhaust fumes from the smelter to produce electricity together with the help of an installed PV plant, in order to reduce the dependency with the electrical network. This electricity will be used to produce hydrogen in an electrolyse, reducing the CO₂ emissions (few natural gas and renewable production of H₂).

Today available PV power alone cannot cover 100% of daily electrical needs, even considering an ideally efficient energy storage system. As a consequence, there are different possibilities that could be considered:

- No additional PV production, but an additional electric production comes from waste heat recovery and conversion to electricity by using an ORC system. This option would increase energy recovery.
- No additional PV production, but an additional electric production comes from waste heat recovery and conversion to electricity by using an ORC system. ETES would be used as a supplementary electricity provider to increase ORC flexibility. This option would both increase renewable energy and energy recovery.

- An additional PV production is considered and an additional electric production comes from waste heat recovery and conversion to electricity by using an ORC system. ETES would be used as a supplementary electricity provider to increase ORC flexibility. This option would both increase renewable energy and energy recovery and reduce or even suppress electricity consumption from the grid. This last option represents a complete autonomous production during a year. With data already provided, a gross assessment of the PV plant size leads to an increase by 300% to cover electricity need for one smelter only.

In the project we will mainly consider the second possibility. The first possibility will be considered as a comparison case and is the object of KPI#T27 (see Chapter 5 below for more details). The third possibility could be investigated in a later phase of the project; nevertheless, some elements are discussed below.

After these introductory remarks, it was chosen to massively use waste heat to permanently produce electricity through an ORC system. The qualitative characteristics of the global energy system are:

- Permanent and stable waste heat,
- Stable need of electricity on the process for H₂ production,
- Intermittent electricity apparent need due to intermittent global supply (solar). We consider the global existing PV plant.

ETES will provide flexibility of ORC electricity production and reduce electricity consumption from the grid.

The Figure 16 provides an understanding to the SEHRENE ETES integration in the whole TORRECID process with a simplified energy flows diagram.

Figure 16 Example of configuration for TOR case

We give here an illustration of a possible use of ETES on a more quantitative basis. The aim of this simple illustration is to provide rough estimations of involved energies and powers, to share main principles of the technical analysis and give elements for the methodology. This will naturally introduce future work for next WP.

- 8 smelters are available, we consider only one.
- Waste heat available for one smelter: 260 kWth. 50 kWe can be produced by ORC system; ~50 kWth are still usable as waste heat.
- Need of electricity on the process for H₂ production: 220 kWe, for one smelter,
- Intermittent electricity apparent need due to intermittent global supply (solar PV). As a first hypothesis we consider that the global PV is available for one smelter.
 - In the worst case (“winter case”), which was first considered:
 - 250 kWe are available during 9h (=2250 kWe.h), due to solar PV.
 - Waste heat comes from ORC and additional waste heat can come directly from other smelters.
 - ETES will charge electricity during 9h hour.
 - ETES charge during day: $9 \times 80 \text{ kWe.h} = 720 \text{ kWe.h}$
 - One additional smelter is needed to provide a sufficient level of waste heat (additional 270kWth needed if COP of heat pump is equal to 5).
 - ETES will discharge electricity during 15h.
 - Considering a RTE of 80% of ETES during night: EHT could discharge 576 kWe.h, additional 38 kWe could be provided by the system during 15h.
 - The electrical network will provide 132kWe during 15h.
 - In a more favorable case (“spring extrapolated case”):
 - 400 kWe are available during 12h (=4800 kWe.h). This hypothesis comes from 1.
 - 5 kWe are used for auxiliary needs or to increase H₂ production during day and night.
 - ETES will charge electricity during 12h hour.
 - ETES charge during day: $12 \times 225 \text{ kWe.h} = 2700 \text{ kWe.h}$
 - 3-4 additional smelters are needed to provide a sufficient level of waste heat (additional 850kWth needed if COP of heat pump is equal to 5).
 - ETES will discharge electricity during 12h.

¹ “Annual Performance Comparison Between Tracking and Fixed Photovoltaic Arrays”, Hadis Moradi, Amir Abtahi and Roger Messenger, 978-1-5090-2724-8/16/\$31.00, 2016 IEEE.

- Considering a RTE of 80% of ETES during night: EHT could discharge 1560 kWe.h, additional 180 kWe could be provided by the system during 12h (night).
- Remark: additional waste heat from smelter(s) could be partially or totally replaced by other waste heat in the facility or moderate temperature solar heat. This last option would ensure a larger renewable energy use.

We repeat that this is a typical example of a possible use of ETES, which has some advantages and drawbacks:

- Advantages: high value of electricity storage, large renewable energy integration
- Drawbacks: requirement of a high value of waste heat, high flexibility for ORC and HP required.

Other images are possible, for example those involving lower values of waste heat and, as a consequence, lower values of stored electricity.

4.2.2.1 Main principles of the technical analysis

Some technical points on the case itself have to be investigated:

- Electricity from the power grid used in TORRECID facility: origin, cost, associated CO2 emissions
- Use of electricity inside TORRECID facility: estimation of auxiliary needs or additional electrolyser
- Smelter waste heat: minimal temperature return, possibility to use smelter waste heat
- Project of extension of PV field and/or creation of a solar thermal energy field

ORC design has to be studied in details in design mode and in large off-design mode.

- Concerning the design mode, we investigate a particular design involving an intermediary thermal loop, which is used to transport smelter gases heat rate from smelter to ORC plant. The corresponding temperature is 200°C approximately in the thermal loop. Cycle optimization is the subject of next WP, but as an example a first calculation of ORC with cyclopentane as a refrigerant is shown below.

Figure 17 Example of simulation results of ORC used in TOR case (for a 1kg/s flowrate)

4.2.2.2 Methodology and future work

Having the technical elements cited below, it is possible to draw a methodology for the specific case study. This methodology could be organized in 4 steps:

- What are the technical elements or specific choices which provide quantitative limitations for the ETES?
 - Limitation due to ORC off-design operation; architecture choices can help to extend off-design operation
 - Limitation due to HP off-design operation
 - Storage size (maximal storage size linked to site requirements or technical constraints)
 - Waste heat use, strategic use of complementary waste heat sources
 - Strategic choices concerning grid electricity
 - Strategic choices concerning PV production
- ETES technical design:
 - Define user-case (winter/spring/summer/autumn) with associated constraints
 - Design of a first reference ETES technical design, based on current work and experimental work

- Derivation of an extended model, based on non-dimensional considerations and relative approach
 - Experimental validation will help to confirm assumptions and results
- Economical and LCA calculations:
 - Evaluation on the first reference ETES image on main KPI
 - Derivation of an extended model
- Optimisation process (EMS):
 - Use of the extended model to find optima
 - Define energy strategy to be included in EMS.

4.3 Use Case 3: CUERVA Electricity Distribution Facility

4.3.1 CUERVA Site Description

Cuerva's core activities are related to the Energy value chain, namely Distribution System Operation (DSO), RE production, energy services, construction and industrial services and energy digitalization services.

The facility is located in the south-east of Spain, in the area of Granada. The picture 18 shows the location on the map:

Figure 18 - Location of Granada in Spain.

Cuerva produces an average annual generation of 96.80 GWh. The installed generation capacity is distributed as follows: 42 MW (2%) from hydroelectric power plants, 63 MW (3%) from wind, and 1,662 MW (95%) from photovoltaic sources.

Cuerva has a grid with a length of 488,4 km (55%) of low voltage, 368,6 km (41%) of medium voltage and 33,4 km (4%) of high voltage. It is connected with REE that is Spanish Electrical Network.

CUERVA as DSO supply power to the province of Granada since 1939, and supplying power to more than 16.000 connection points.

4.3.1.1 Living lab

There is a Living Lab in one part of the grid, that is quite digitized, and provides real-time knowledge of behaviour in order to improve the quality of supply, increase resilience and optimise its operation and control, always seeking to be prepared for future scenarios. Low Voltage and Medium Voltage networks have integrated Smart Meters for each consumer, Advanced Supervisors in every LV/MV Transformer and a DT of the low-voltage grid, all of which allow Cuerva to have full knowledge of the grid's status.

Figure 19 - Living Lab. Technical infrastructure available

4.3.1.2 CITAI Industrial Park

In a portion of the Cuerva Living Lab is located the CITAI industry park, in Escúzar, a small village located in Granada's metropolitan area, but isn't owned by Cuerva. This industry park is supplied by Cuerva, who is the DSO, and will be included in the demo as Use Case. The CITAI park covers an area of 4 million square meters and there is still a lot of unbuilt land. The number of companies and industries is expected to increase in the coming years, in fact, currently is being built the particle accelerator IFMIF-DONES, a singular scientific facility to study fusion energy. This facility will be one of the most important research infrastructures in Spain and will require a high demand for electricity.

Figure 20 - View of the CITAI industrial park

Figure 21 - Location of the CITAI Park in the Cuerva grid.

Figure 22 - CITAI Industrial Park grid.

Currently, in the park there are in total 51 companies: 43 are in operation and 8 companies are being built. Therefore, there are 51 supply points and a maximum contracted power over 19 MW.

The following table 4 shows the operating companies located in the industrial park with the contracted electrical power and the installed PV power for self-consumption:

Table 4 Companies in the CITAI park, contracted electricity power and installed PV self-consumption.

Sector	Reference Number	Voltage	Maximum Contracted Power (kW)	Installed PV Power (kW) (self-consumption)
Automotive	1	400	95	30
	2	400	15	NA
Catering	3	400	60	25
Chemical	4	400	100	NA
Construction	5	20.000	700	NA
	6	400	145	NA
	7	400	30	NA
	8	400	10	NA
Curtain manufacturing	9	400	90	NA
Electricity distribution	10	400	30	NA
Food	11	20.000	2.000	NA
	12	20.000	1.440	480
	13	20.000	1.000	200
	14	20.000	740	360
	15	20.000	630	100
	16	20.000	350	240
	17	20.000	340	NA
	18	20.000	280	100
	19	20.000	260	NA
	20	20.000	180	100
Food	21	20.000	180	200
	22	400	50	NA
	23	400	50	NA
	24	400	45	NA

	25	400	25	NA
	26	400	15	NA
IT	27	20.000	400	200
Logistics	28	20.000	3.690	100
	29	20.000	220	NA
	30	400	20	NA
Metal	31	400	110	NA
	32	400	50	NA
Paper and plastic	33	20.000	1.250	340
	34	20.000	1.070	500
	35	20.000	760	NA
	36	400	220	NA
	37	400	85	NA
Pharmaceutical	38	20.000	2.500	100
Quality	39	400	30	20
Real estate	40	400	7	NA
Research	41	400	100	NA
Technology Park	42	400	95	8
Water	43	20.000	260	45

4.3.1.3 Energy prices

Twenty-one of these companies, which have a large consumption of electricity and medium voltage, have contracted a 6.1TD electricity tariff. This tariff has six periods, each with a different energy price. Each company can choose and schedule these six electricity price periods according to its production and consumption needs, in order to make the energy price more profitable.

The standard prices for the 6.1TD tariff in the year 2024 are shown in Table 5, where each TE is a period. These prices include taxes.

Table 5 Standard prices for the 6.1TD tariff in the year 2024 (include taxes).

Net Energy Term- €/kWh					
TE1	TE2	TE3	TE4	TE5	TE6
0,318	0,300	0,301	0,299	0,289	0,254

Ice-cream factory

An example of an industry located in the CITAI industrial park could be a company dedicated to the manufacture of ice cream. Specifically, it is company 16 shown in Table 4, with a contracted power of 350 kW and a 240 kW PV power installation for self-consumption.

The diagram below gives an overview of a general process in ice cream manufacture.

Figure 23 - A Typical Ice Cream Mix Plant.

1. Mixing of Ingredients

Basic Ingredients: Ingredients such as milk, cream, sugar, and stabilizers/emulsifiers are combined.

Mixing: The ingredients are mixed in large stainless-steel tanks to ensure a homogeneous mixture.

2. Pasteurization

Heating: The mixture is heated to a high temperature (typically around 80°C) for a specific time (around 15-30 seconds).

Cooling: The mixture is then rapidly cooled to about 4°C to kill microorganisms and prevent bacterial growth.

3. Homogenization

The pasteurized mixture passes through a homogenizer, which reduces the size of fat particles and evenly distributes the ingredients. This results in a smooth and creamy texture.

4. Maturation

The mixture is stored at a low temperature (4°C) for several hours (typically 4-24 hours). This step allows the stabilizers and emulsifiers to work properly and improves the final texture of the ice cream.

5. Freezing and Churning

Initial Freezing: The mixture is introduced into a continuous freezer that partially freezes the mixture while churning it.

During this process, air is incorporated into the mixture to create a light and airy texture. The amount of air incorporated is called "overrun" and can vary depending on the type of ice cream.

This process ends when the right texture is achieved and the ice cream is at -10°C.

6. Final Freezing

The partially frozen ice cream is sent to hardening freezers at very low temperatures (-40°C to -60°C) to complete the freezing process. This step ensures that the ice cream reaches the proper consistency and remains stable during storage and distribution.

7. Packaging, Storage, and Distribution

Annual energy consumption of the ice cream factory (2023)

This section shows the electricity consumption of industry 16 in Table 4 for the year 2023.

Table 6 Contracted power

Supply point voltage (V)	Installation max power (kW)	PV Installation max power (kW)
20.000	350	240

Table 7 Energy consumption in 2023

Total annual imported energy (kWh)	Total annual exported energy (kWh)	% Annual energy exported	Total annual generated and self-consumed PV energy (kWh)	Total annual energy consumption (kWh)
819.089	136	0,0003	439.380	1.258.469 (35% is self-consumption)

Monthly energy consumed 2023 (kWh)

Figure 24 Monthly energy consumption in 2023

The following graphs show the average energy consumption in different months in 2023: January, April, July and October. The data integrate the imported grid energy plus the PV energy generated and self-supplied every hour.

Average daily energy consumption. January 2023

Figure 25 Average daily energy consumption, January 2023

Average daily energy consumption. April 2023

Figure 26 Average daily energy consumption, April 2023

Average daily energy consumption. July 2023

Figure 27 Daily average energy consumption, July 2023

Average daily energy consumption. October 2023

Figure 28 Daily average energy consumption, October 2023

4.3.2 ETES Integration to CUERVA Facility

The integration of ETES in the industries located in the CITAI industrial park will allow:

- In the industries:
 - Reduce grid energy consumption.
 - Increasing energy efficiency.
 - Maximise the use of the PV energy generated.
 - To reduce the electricity bill in industry by using their own energy resources when the price of electricity is more expensive.
 - To use waste heat from processes that is currently not being used.

In the grid:

- The quality of electricity supply will increase and become more stable.
- The electricity supply will be more flexible due to:
 - Congestion and overvoltage in the grid will be avoided.
 - It will respond to demand by adjusting the use of electricity according to customer consumption.
 - ETES will allow the storage of excess energy in industries when generation exceeds grid demand, and its release when demand exceeds generation.

5. Definition of KPIs for the assessment of the use cases regarding the SEHRENE ETES concept

5.1 SEHRENE main KPIs

The main objectives regarding the SEHRENE projects are:

- OBJ#1 To design an integrated ETES concept at TRL4
- OBJ#2 To maximize ETES performance
- OBJ#3 To ensure reliability
- OBJ#4 To ensure economic viability
- OBJ#5 To ensure environmental sustainability
- OBJ#6 To develop Digital Twin of ETES related to use cases
- OBJ#7 To Provide EMS for ETES
- OBJ#8 To engage stakeholders to invest after SEHRENE
- OBJ#9 To achieve a Market entry by 2030

In accordance with the main objectives of the project according to the DoA, main KPI are defined and presented in Table below.

Table 8 – List of the SEHRENE KPIs

KPI	Description
KPI#1	3 DTs (1 per use-case) of integrated ETES concept with 1 single fluid loop combining (i) a new design of HP up to 200°C, (ii) novel PCM TES working as condenser (up to 200°C) and evaporator (up to 190°C) and (iii) ORC
KPI#2	Two lab scale prototypes: (i) TRL4 ETES prototype coupling 20 kWth-scale HP, TES at 20 kWh, with a lab scale ORC turbine at 1 kW _e and (ii) TRL5 TES prototype for cycling of TES from 160-200°C over 1500 cycles
KPI#3	Round-trip efficiencies (RTE) of 80% for TOR, 85% for ZOREN, 80% for CUERVA
KPI#4	Heat-Pump Coefficient of Performance (COP) = 50% of theoretical maximum COP
KPI#5	TES energy density of 90 kWh/m ³ (+30% vs SoA PCM TES)
KPI#6	Storage 48h (vs 4-6h for Li-ion ⁶), ETES enables longer duration storage via scale-up.
KPI#7	No change in RTE over 1500 cycles in prototype, 2-3x longer lifetime than Li-ion
KPI#8	ORC start-up time reduced from 1 h to several minutes for rapid return to electricity
KPI#9	Corrosion rate of novel metallic foam <0.1mm/year, giving a TES lifetime of >30 years since a >3mm corrosion allowance is incorporated in the Kelvin lattice design
KPI#10	No failure in the novel Kelvin lattice under stress (50% AYS/0.2% proof stress)

KPI#11	PCM durability (x168 hours aging tests)
KPI#12	TEA shows LCOS lower than pumped hydro, the lowest cost commercial storage.
KPI#13	TEA shows at-scale CAPEX lower than Li-ion (which is 700-1300 €/kWh)
KPI#14	LCA will show NG and CO2 avoided (90 Mm3 of NG and 15Mt CO2/year by 2040)
KPI#15	Increased use of RE (reduced curtailment) by 13% in TOR use-case (for 1 smelter)
KPI#16	No CRM use, WF with ultra-low GWP (<10) and net-zero ozone depletion potential
KPI#17	More favourable LCA than (i) Li-ion and (ii) green H2 energy storage and recovery
KPI#18	Recyclability via existing sorting and recycling technologies
KPI#19	Discrepancy between the DT and the results of the accurate physical models below 5%
KPI#20	The DT control capability will solve the system performance in less than 1 second
KPI#21	6-month test phase of developed algorithms, to detect and correct possible events that produce failures or errors, and to verify that the system is robust and adequate
KPI#22	<10% estimated long-term error, computed, with MAPE, MAE, or sMAPE
KPI#23	Decision-Support System (TEA and LCA) used by 20 companies before the end of SEHRENE to evaluate the interest of investing in upscaling the ETES after the project
KPI#24	>8 Companies commit before the end of SEHRENE to its upscaling: >1 DSOs; >1 RE producers; >1 HP manufacturer; >1 ORC manufacturer; >2 EII end-users; >1 metal foam manufacturer and >1 engineering firm to assemble the whole ETES
KPI#25	No geographical limitations to ETES
KPI#26	ETES materials and components based on existing / commercially viable (MRL 9-10) processes for TES, ORC and heat-pump manufacturing enabling rapid mass production as soon as SEHRENE's ETES is upscaled/replicated via a large-scale demonstration after the project

5.2 SEHRENE use cases KPIs

Each use case will be studied and evaluated through some of the KPI defined above. In some cases, new KPI are added to cover the specificity of the site. The following chapters describes the KPI that will be assessed and how they will be.

5.2.1 ZORLU use case

The KPI regarding ZORLU use case are listed in the table below.

Table 9 – KPIs identified in ZORLU use case

Id.	Description	Unit	Measurement
KPI#1	HP capacity TES capacity ORC capacity	MW MWh MW	Assessment and energy data calculations
KPI#3	RTE definition and target (85%)	%	Assessment
KPI#4	Minimum HP COP >50%	-	Assessment
KPI#5	TES energy density	kWh/m ³	Design and assessment
KPI#12	LCOS definition and target	€/MWh	Assessment
KPI#13	CAPEX at scale lower than Li-Ion	€/kWh	Assessment
KPI#16	No CRM and low GWP and no ODP working fluid	Chemical evaluation	Assessment
KPI#17	Specific comparison to Li-Ion	€/MWh	Assessment

5.2.2 TORRECID use case

The KPI regarding TORRECID use case are listed in the table below.

Table 10 – KPIs identified in TORRECID use case

Id.	Description	Unit	Measurement
KPI#1	HP capacity TES capacity ORC capacity	MW MWh MW	Assessment and energy data calculations
KPI#3	RTE definition and target (80%)	%	Assessment
KPI#4	Minimum HP COP >50%	-	Assessment
KPI#5	TES energy density	kWh/m ³	Design and assessment
KPI#12	LCOS definition and target	€/MWh	Assessment
KPI#13	CAPEX at scale lower than Li-Ion	€/kWh	Assessment
KPI#14	Natural gas and CO ₂ emissions avoided	Nm ³ /year Mt-eqCO ₂ /year	Assessment and gas consumption measurement on site
KPI#15	Increased use of RE	% or MWh/year	Assessment and RE production measurement on site
KPI#16	No CRM and low GWP and no ODP working fluid	Chemical evaluation	Assessment
KPI#17	Specific comparison to Li-Ion	MWh/h	Assessment

Id. Specific KPI for TOR use case	Description	Unit	Measurement
KPI#T27	Specific comparison to single ORC+TES (direct recovery on waste heat)	ORC and TES: MW and MWh LCOE: €/MWh	Assessment and energy data calculations
KPI#T28	Productivity of smelters	Tons/year	Weighting
KPI#T29	Quality of frit produced	Chemical composition	FRX measurement
KPI#T30	Surface needed for ETES	m ²	Data layout

5.2.3 CUERVA use case

The KPI regarding CUERVA use case are listed in the table below.

Table 11 - KPIs identified in CUERVA use case

Id.	Description	Unit	Measurement
KPI#1	HP capacity TES capacity ORC capacity	MW MWh MW	Assessment and energy data calculations
KPI#3	RTE definition and target (80%)	%	Assessment
KPI#4	Minimum HP COP >50%	-	Assessment
KPI#5	TES energy density	kWh/m ³	Design and assessment
KPI#12	LCOS definition and target	€/MWh	Assessment
KPI#13	CAPEX at scale lower than Li-Ion	€/kWh	Assessment
KPI#16	No CRM and low GWP and no ODP working fluid	Chemical evaluation	Assessment
KPI#17	Specific comparison to Li-Ion	€/MWh	Assessment

6. Conclusion

SEHRENE Project aims to develop an ETES system within the project. However, a broader goal is to create reliable industries in terms of both sides of power supply. It is visible from the D2.1 “Requirement Analysis” that integration of ETES technology across different industries increases the sustainability of the system and is enhancing the efficiency of the existing infrastructure. The common challenges industries face today such as energy intermittency and grid stability are addressed and site-specific solutions can be generated. By applying storage of excess energy during periods of low demand and utilizing it when demand is at peak ETES optimizes the energy usage and mitigates fluctuations and its consequences such as price volatility in power market. With the peak shaving and diverse storage options, ETES not only helps with the financial aspects, but also helps with carbon emissions and climate change.

Integration of ETES, especially in energy dependent/sensitive industries, optimizes the energy management and, with the increased efficiency thanks to SEHRENE Project, reduces the operational costs. It creates options for industries with excess energy generated due to high temperature operations and helps minimizing the carbon footprint by doing so. The flexibility of the operations, with the efficiency added value, ETES proves to be a very valuable asset for these defined industries.

Moreover, integration and application of ETES not only helps with the end users but also the grid itself. As the industries become more self-reliant on high demand periods, grid operators gain the ability to react to sudden changes in the grid easier. ETES plays a supporting role to the balancing supply/demand curve of the grid. This also help stabilizing the network, increasing reliability of the distribution system operators. The ETES abilities can also create a pathway for reserve and frequency markets for renewable energy, concretizing its position in energy market.

To sum up, “Requirement Analysis” deliverable is generated with the help of various partners to help enlighten the path for the integration of the ETES that will be developed in this project, with increased flexibility and efficiency. These efforts, with site specific analysis and collaborative input from partners, will ensure a seamless integration and implementation of ETES, addressing many problems and challenges across sectors.

SEHRENE